

REINCARNATE

D1.4 – Integrated information management for circular value flow planning

Project Title	Reincarnation of construction products and materials by slowing down and extending life cycles.
Project Acronym	Reincarnate
Grant Agreement No	101056773
Instrument	Research & Innovation Action
Topic	HORIZON-CL4-2021-TWIN-TRANSITION-01-11
Start Date of Project	June 1, 2022
Duration of Project	48 months

Name of the deliverable	Integrated information management for circular value flow planning
Number of the deliverable	D1.4
Related WP number and name	WP1
Related task number and name	Task1.4 Circular Value Flow Planning Module
Deliverable dissemination level	R – Document, report, PU - Public
Deliverable due date	31.05.2025
Deliverable submission date	19/5 2025
Task leader/Main author	Ragn-Sells

Contributing partners	Demo, Mainflux, TU Berlin, 3L, TU Delft, BUNDESANSTALT FUER MATERIALFORSCHUNG UND -PRUEFUNG
Reviewer(s)	Mustostal, Demo

Abstract

This deliverable D1.4 highlights the challenges connected to reuse and recycling of construction and demolition waste in the EU and describes the method and tools needed to enable circular value flow planning. Further, this deliverable explains the innovation BIM for circular value flow planning and dives deeper into the material path of flat glass, which is used as case for demonstrating the innovation in work package 5.

This deliverable also presents the different data flow hypothesis for enabling BIM for circular value flow planning within the context of flat glass recycling, also diving deeper into the possibilities of reuse of flat glass.

Keywords

Circular Economy, Value flow planning, Building Information Modelling (BIM), Flat glass, Concrete, SLAMD, Data Flow

Revisions

Version	Submission date	Comments	Author
v0.0	12.12.2024	Shared table of content and report structure with contributors	RAS
v0.1	10.04.2025	First draft version sent for initial review	RAS
V0.2	19.04.2025	Second draft version sent for review	RAS
V0.3	23.04.2025	Final draft sent for review	RAS
V0.4	30.05.2025	Final Submission	RAS

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
API	Application programming interface
GUI	Graphical User Interface
BIM	Building information modelling
LOD	Level of detail
CDW	Construction and demolition waste
CE	Circular Economy
CP-IM	Circular Potential Information Platform
CRM	Customer relationship management
CVFP	Circular value flow planning
BIM-CVFP	BIM for circular value flow planning
DFM	Data flow model
EoW	End of waste
ERP	Enterprise resource planning
EWS	European Waste Catalogue
PAE	Primary Application Energy
PLM	Product lifecycle management
XRF	X-ray fluorescence
LIDAR	Light Detection and Ranging

POI	Point of interest
NDT	Non-destructive testing
CO2e	Carbon dioxide equivalents
LCA	Life cycle analysis

Reincarnate project

The average lifespan of a building is 39 years — in Europe, it is only 25-30 years — and the main reason for demolition is obsolescence. This is why there is a large amount of Construction and demolition waste (CDW), representing approximately 25-30% of all waste in Europe, in addition to that generated in current construction works.

The recycling rate for CDW is relatively high (above 75%). This activity generated \$126.89 billion in 2019, Europe contributed the largest share, almost two-fifths of the total global market and is projected to reach \$149.19 billion by 2027. Unfortunately, many of the most valuable materials in CDW cannot be meaningfully separated and end up in landfills.

This helps to get an idea of the efficiency potential for climate neutrality that exists in construction.

Reincarnate aims at advancing circular economy practices within the European construction industry and enabling to significantly maximise the life cycle of buildings, construction products and materials, reduce CDW by 80%, increase the reusability of buildings, construction products and materials and, as a result, lower the sector's emissions by 70%.

As a result of these actions, Reincarnate will significantly advance circular economy practices within the European construction industry.

First, it will create a Circular Potential Information Management (CP-IM) platform and a set of innovations to use it. These solutions will draw upon emerging digital technologies, such as digital twin representation, artificial intelligence, and robotic automation.

3 empirically proven social science insights will allow fostering widespread adoption of reused high-quality construction products and materials, and business eco-system development frameworks to combine actors within sustainable value chains. All innovations will be demonstrated on eleven selected real-world projects and value chains. Furthermore, business process guidelines and an e-learning platform will be developed to drive the dissemination and exploitation of the Reincarnate results.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of the deliverable

Reincarnate aims at advancing circular economy practices within the European construction industry and enabling to significantly maximise the life cycle of buildings, construction products and materials, reduce construction and demolition waste (CDW) by 80%, increase the reusability of buildings, construction products and materials and, as a result, lower the sector's emissions by 70%.

Currently, buildings in Europe have a relatively short average lifespan of just 25–30 years, compared to a global average of 39 years. The predominant reason for demolition is not structural failure, but functional or economic obsolescence. As a result, construction and demolition waste (CDW) has become a critical issue, representing approximately 25–30% of all waste generated across the EU. This presents both a significant environmental challenge and a tremendous opportunity for systemic change.

The circular economy (CE) offers a compelling response. By minimizing waste and promoting reuse, remanufacturing, and high-value recycling, CE strategies can significantly reduce material consumption and environmental impact. The core principle is to design regenerative systems that slow (extend product life), close (enable end-of-life reuse), and narrow (increase material efficiency) material and energy loops, thereby mitigating resource depletion and emissions¹. However, the challenge lies in the legacy of a linear construction paradigm. The current stock of buildings and materials was designed without consideration for future reuse or circular value flows. As such, we lack sufficient data on the quantity, quality, and traceability of materials embedded in the built environment—data that is critical for creating viable circular supply chains. This gap is further compounded by existing waste legislation, which tends to reinforce linear processes by emphasizing disposal and recycling over reuse and regeneration. In this

¹ Ntalianas, E. (2019). *The future building envelope: Circular and adaptive* [Master's thesis, Delft University of Technology]. TU Delft Repository. <https://repository.tudelft.nl/record/uuid:5e187ce8-7c67-4644-b30e-17bbda1c736a>

deliverable we explore *Circular Value Flow Planning* (CVFP) as a strategic approach to reconnect circular supply with demand. By developing methods to map, track, and assess materials and their flows. Using CVFP we aim to overcome informational and systemic barriers to reuse and recycling. The purpose is to explore how digital tools, data infrastructures, and stakeholder collaboration can enable the predictive, high-quality reuse of materials, thus transforming waste into value within a circular construction economy.

1.2. Structure of this report

This deliverable D 1.4 'Integrated information management for circular value flow planning', is part of Work Package 1, the "REINCARNATE CP-IM". It focuses on different processes to manage information to allow for the strategic management of circular value flows. The introduction of this deliverable, chapter 1, contains the purpose, the structure of the report and how this deliverable relates to other tasks within REINCARNATE. Chapter 2 explains the challenges connected to reuse and recycling of construction and demolition waste. The chapter also explains the guiding questions of this deliverable and explains the concept of circular value flow planning.

In chapter 3, methodology, tools and methods used to define and map out the material path and data flow for specific products are presented. Further, different technologies and tools that will be used for the demonstrations are also presented. The use cases that are the focus of this deliverable, the subsequent innovation and demonstrations are presented and explained in chapter 4 and in chapter 5 we dive deeper into the innovation BIM for circular value flow planning. Chapter 6 explains how this deliverable connects to general theme of work package 1 and digs deeper into the CP-IM platform. Finally, chapter 7 digs deeper into the circular value flows that we aim to demonstrate in work package 5. We present the material path of flat glass and methods with their connected data flow hypothesis which the demonstrations 'Inventory of the material bank', 'SLAMD' and 'Flat glass to flat glass' aim to verify.

1.3. Relation to other tasks in the project

As shown in the Figure 1 below WP1, the task 1.4 Circular Value Flow Planning Module is a part of WP1. There has been a lot of cooperation with T1.1 Ontologies, information model

and valuation, to develop the ontologies used in this deliverable and build the foundation onto several scenarios that are suggested in this deliverable. This is the key in the innovation related to this deliverable and will be demonstrated in WP5 and implemented in the CP-IM. Discussions have been held with all other actors focusing on windows and concrete in relation to T2.3, T2.4, T3.2, T3.3. The work performed in WP4 has fed the implementation of the data flow developed and how this can increase circular innovation and business models.

The Task 1.4 Circular Value Flow Planning Module has been developed by Ragn-Sells along with its contributing partners. The outcome of WP1 will, along with innovations and tasks from WP2, WP3 and WP4, be demonstrated in WP5.

T1.4 will be demonstrated in 3 different demonstrations; “Digital inventory of the material bank”, “SLAMD” and “Flat glass to flat glass”.

Figure 1: Connection of D1.4 to other work packages

2. Background and Context

2.1. Challenges in Reuse and Recycling

Every year, about 100 billion tonnes of raw material is extracted and used in the world, compared to 30 billion tonnes in 1970. Global material extraction is steadily increasing with an average growth of 2.3%.²

At the same time, only 7.2 percent of the global economy is circular, meaning that it consists of materials that have already been used, replacing virgin materials. In 2018, this number was 9.1 percent. Despite increased recycling, the world has rapidly become less circular since the extraction of virgin materials has increased so much faster³.

According to The UN Global Resource Outlook 2024 extraction and processing of material resources accounts for at 55% of greenhouse gas emissions (additional 5% if land use change is included), and 90% of biodiversity loss and water stress. As traditional sources for raw materials become increasingly depleted, it takes more and more energy to extract the same amount and material quality. Similarly, many other forms of pressure on the planet also increase, such as the use of land and the amount of pollution. Circularity within construction and the built environment faces a vast number of challenges. The challenges highlighted in subsequent chapters are:

- Legislation
- Knowledge in requirements
- Data standards
- Project complexity
- Lack of information

2.1.1. Legislation

The current EU framework⁴ for managing construction and demolition waste (CDW) is largely shaped by waste legislation, which emphasizes sorting rather than recycling or reuse. According to this regulation, CDW must be separated into six categories—glass,

² United Nations Environment Programme. (2024). *Global resource outlook 2024*. United Nations. <https://www.resourcepanel.org/reports/global-resources-outlook-2024>

³ Circle Economy. (2023). *The circularity gap report 2023*. <https://www.circularity-gap.world/2023>

⁴ European Parliament, & Council of the European Union. (2008). *Directive 2008/98/EC on waste and repealing certain directives (consolidated version 05/07/2018)*. EUR-Lex. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:02008L0098-20180705>

wood, plastic, metal, inert materials, and plaster—directly at the source. While this sorting is essential for compliance, it often results in mixed waste streams that are difficult to recycle into high-value applications. A study of 36 Norwegian construction projects by Fufa et al. (2023)⁵ highlights this disconnect: despite an impressive average sorting rate of 89%, the average recycling rate reached only 32%⁶.

Complicating matters further, current building regulations continue to prioritize new materials over recycled or reused ones. Projects that attempt to integrate reclaimed or recycled components often encounter longer approval processes, increased insurance costs, and heightened uncertainty around liability. One of the key obstacles is the lack of clear procedures for guaranteeing the performance and safety of reused components. Without consistent frameworks for warranty and certification, both clients and insurers remain hesitant, thereby limiting wider adoption of reuse practices—despite their environmental potential.

Unlike new materials, which come with established certifications and warranties, reused products often lack such assurances, leading to hesitancy among stakeholders regarding their reliability and compliance with safety standards)

2.1.2. Knowledge in requirements

In Sweden, a significant barrier to advancing circular construction practices is the limited knowledge among clients—particularly public and private developers—on how to effectively specify requirements for reused and recycled materials in procurement processes. This knowledge gap often results in the continued preference for new materials, thereby stalling demand for reused products or products with recycled content and hindering the development of a circular economy within the construction sector. A study by MSc students at Chalmers University of Technology in 2023 underscores this issue, revealing that many actors are uncertain about how to formulate and implement recycling or reuse requirements in practice. The absence of

⁵ Fufa, S. M., et.al. (2023). Waste free construction site—A buzzword, nice to have or more. *Resources, Conservation & Recycling Advances*, 18, 200149. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rcradv.2023.200149>

⁶Fufa, S. M., Fjellheim, K., Venås, C., Vevatne, J. T., Kummen, T. M., & Henke, L. (2023). *Waste free construction site – A buzzword, nice to have or more* [PDF]. SINTEF. <https://sintef.brage.unit.no/sintef-xmlui/bitstream/handle/11250/3065658/1-s2.0-S2667378923000214-main.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

clear guidelines and standardized procedures contributes to this uncertainty, making it challenging for clients to confidently include such materials in their projects.⁷

This challenge is not unique to Sweden; it reflects a broader issue across the European Union. The EU's regulatory framework for reclaimed building elements is marked by inconsistencies and a lack of harmonization, which creates legal uncertainties and inhibits the widespread implementation of reuse strategies. The absence of clear standards for the documentation, certification, and quality assessment of reused materials exacerbates these challenges, making it difficult for stakeholders to navigate the complexities of integrating such components into construction projects⁸.

2.1.3. Data standards

In Sweden, pre-demolition audits are legally required to assess the reuse potential of building components before any renovation or demolition work begins. However, although legislation mandates these audits, it does not specify how they must be conducted or which data fields are essential, leading to widely varying practices among auditors⁹. Across the EU, the EU Construction & Demolition Waste Management Protocol recommends conducting pre-demolition audits to identify hazardous materials and reuse opportunities but stops short of prescribing detailed procedures or data requirements¹⁰. Furthermore, both Swedish and EU waste statistics rely on broad European Waste Catalogue (EWC) codes which groups materials into broad waste categories.. Consequently, the statistics and data available lacks comparability, granularity and is not suitable for effective planning and implementation of circular flows of construction materials¹¹. Assuming it is businesses that will develop and implement circular solutions within the CDW space, the harmonized audit

⁷Formas. (n.d.). *The power of procurement: How requirements of reuse can accelerate circular construction in Sweden*. <https://www.formas.se/en/financing/current-calls/calls/2022-11-17-the-power-of-procurement--how-requirements-of-reuse-can-accelerate-circular-construction-in-sweden.html>

⁸ Condotta, M., & Zatta, E. (2021). Reuse of building elements in the architectural practice and the European regulatory context: Inconsistencies and possible improvements. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 318, 128413. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.128413>

⁹ Wahlström, M., et.al. (2019). *Improving quality of construction & demolition waste: Requirements for pre-demolition audit*. Nordic Council of Ministers. <https://www.norden.org/en/publication/improving-quality-construction-demolition-waste-requirements-pre-demolition-audit>

¹⁰ European Commission. (2018). *Guidelines for the waste audits before demolition and renovation works of buildings EU Construction and Demolition Waste Management*. https://ec.europa.eu/environment/waste/studies/pdf/guidelines_demolition_renovation.pdf

¹¹ EU commission (2018), *Guidelines for the waste audits before demolition and renovation works of buildings EU Construction and Demolition Waste Management*

methodologies and more detailed classification systems at both national and EU levels would be an enabler. For circular material paths within starting from the built environment a better granularity of the data and the material is a prerequisite¹².

2.1.4. Project complexity

The construction industry is often described as fragmented and difficult to coordinate¹³. Challenges that stem from the very nature of project-based business. Its core characteristics: uniqueness, discontinuity, and complexity, introduce structural and operational hurdles¹⁴. These challenges frequently manifest in decoupled processes and a lack of integration across the value chain¹⁵. Multi-partner projects, common in renovation and demolition, add further temporal complexity, making collaboration even more difficult¹⁶. As a result, supply chain performance tends to suffer. Research suggests that not only the structure of the industry but also the way organizations collaborate internally may be contributing to the sector's slow progress toward circularity and sustainability¹⁷. In essence, the diversity and unpredictability of construction project setups make effective supply management inherently difficult.

2.1.5. The lack of information

Information and data availability represent a critical bottleneck in circular construction practices. Throughout a product's lifecycle, datasets are generated (e.g., specifications, quantities, performance records). Upon handover of a new building, owners receive extensive documentation on maintenance schedules, design drawings, and operational systems. However, these documents rarely capture material-level details needed for circular reuse (e.g., precise glass formulations, structural component provenance) and are often stored without systematic preservation. Consequently, when buildings undergo renovation or demolition, vital information for high-quality recycling is

¹² Byggmaterialindustrierna. (2025). *Vägen mot mer cirkulära byggmaterialflöden – Byggmaterialindustriernas perspektiv*. Byggmaterialindustrierna. <https://byggmaterialindustrierna.se/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/Byggmaterialindustrierna-Rapport-cirkular-ekonomi-jan-2025.pdf>

¹³ Bankvall, L., Bygballe, L. E., Dubois, A. & Jahre, M. 2010. Interdependence in supply chains and projects in construction. *Supply Chain Management-an International Journal*, 15, 385-393.

¹⁴ Sandhu, M. & Helo, P. 2006. A network approach to project business analysis. *Engineering Construction and Architectural Management*, 13, 600-+.

¹⁵ Bankvall, L., Bygballe, L. E., Dubois, A. & Jahre, M. 2010. Interdependence in supply chains and projects in construction. *Supply Chain Management-an International Journal*, 15, 385-393.

¹⁶ Havinga, F., Mahdad, M. & Dolfsma, W. 2023. Unpacking ecosystem dynamics in the construction industry: The transition toward circular construction ecosystems. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 414.

¹⁷ Havinga, F., Mahdad, M. & Dolfsma, W. 2023. Unpacking ecosystem dynamics in the construction industry: The transition toward circular construction ecosystems. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 414.

missing¹⁸. Moreover, no standardized protocols exist to facilitate data exchange between facility owners and waste management firms, leading to fragmented, non-interoperable datasets that impede informed, business-level decision-making.

2.2. Guiding questions for this deliverable

- Where, in each supply chain, should data and information be created/added/kept for the material or product to enable recycling or reuse?
- How do we keep or add information in a cost-effective way?
- How do we use this information to create new or better circular solutions (upstream, production, downstream)?
- What tools and methods can we use to measure and create enough information for decision making?

2.3. Concept of Circular value flow planning

To address the challenges mentioned in chapter 2.1 A systems approach is necessary for effectively linking the supply of the resources within the built environment to the demand of products and materials in the producing industry. In practice, circular value flow planning is utilized to realize the systems approach mentioned. The purpose of circular value flow planning is to ensure that materials are used in the most resource efficient way throughout multiple life cycles. This means that materials and products can keep, or even increase, the value on a system level over time. This can for example be to maintain a material quality through an entire life cycle and not being downgraded or that the material is used in such a way so the application of it has a greater value for the user than in its previous application. It can also be enhancing material and products value by adding data and information through inventory combined with destructive and non-destructive testing, supporting prospecting of circular materials.

With Circular value flow planning the relevant information related to a material will be kept through the value chain. The information that is needed at a specific step of the circular process will be available for the actor who needs it. Circular value flow planning

¹⁸ Chandran, R., & Joseph, N. (2023). *Information Flow in Reuse Prospects of Construction Materials: Analysis of information flow in the Swedish construction industry*. Uppsala University. <https://uu.diva-portal.org/smash/record.jsf?pid=diva2%3A1769269>

is used to identify the relevant information to make circular material paths possible and scalable. With the right information kept, added, and created critical calculations and predictions can be made on how to use the built environment as a feedstock for a circular construction industry. Basically, buyers should be able to buy materials and goods in the same way as they do with virgin materials today, even if the material is recycled or reused.

To enable the circulation of materials, we believe that the circular value flow planning module in the CP-IM platform should:

- Help users understand what data they need to collect from the built environment (material bank)
- Help user understand supply and demand of recycled material stock
- Help user select best recycling path for material
- Data as a means for making better decisions
- Help the user understand the climate benefits of circular material paths by providing CO2 information about the material

3. Methodology

This chapter outlines the research design, data collection procedures, and analytical techniques employed in the study. A mixed-methods approach was adopted to ensure both quantitative rigor and qualitative depth. Data was collected through structured surveys and in-depth interviews and analysed using statistical software and thematic coding. All steps aimed to ensure reproducibility and transparency.

3.1. Process overview

To initiate Circular Value Flow Planning, several key steps must be undertaken. First, the target material and its corresponding material path (the physical flow of the material) must be identified and clearly defined. Once the physical flow is established, the requisite data streams and their directions are specified. These foundational activities constitute the essence of Circular Value Flow Planning, as they involve mapping the stakeholders, processes, and information requirements at each stage of the material's journey.

Defining the physical flow also entails establishing its scope and constraints. Stakeholders must articulate the system boundaries and underlying assumptions. Circular value flow planning can be applied on a closed-loop flow with known, fixed steps or for an exploratory open-loop flow in which boundaries and parameters remain provisional.

The process for identifying the data requirements of Circular Value Flow Planning comprises the following steps:

1. Chose the material/product to focus on
2. Define the boundaries
3. Define the physical steps
4. Define the values of the circular material path
5. Define the enables for creating and capturing value in the circular material path
6. Define activities and actors in the circular material path
7. Define data and information needs
8. Define and/or develop an ontology
9. Describe the data flow and connect to activities in the circular material path
10. Iterate

As can be seen in Figure 2

Figure 2. The defined steps to identify circular value flow planning and the questions to answer in each step. (See appendix IV for high resolution image)

The methodology developed for Reincarnate has been discussed with other research project looking at circularity and traceability to identify synergies and potential differences such as Trace4value and Onto-DESIDE.

One key factor is to include several perspectives when defining and iterating the process and defining what data to collect. The stakeholders in the chosen material path are key actors to secure a collaboration within order to enable the collection and verify the quality of the material as well as the data..

3.1.1. The practical steps needed for enabling circular value flow planning

The steps needed and guiding questions are summarized in Table 1.

Step	Name	Key questions
1.	Chose the material/ product to focus on	
2.	Define the boundaries	What physical steps and actors are maintaining the current linear material path?

		<p>What does the regulatory landscape look like?</p> <p>How will the regulatory landscape change?</p>
3.	Define the physical steps	<p>What are physical steps are crucial to enable a circular material path?</p> <p>What steps are required for a high-quality recycling process?</p>
4.	Define the values of the circular material path	What values do we want to create or capture in each step of the material path?
5.	Define the enables for creating and capturing value in the circular material path	What needs to be true to enable value creation?
6.	Define activities and actors in the circular material path	<p>What activities are needed in the new circular material path?</p> <p>What actor is responsible for each activity?</p>
7.	Define data and information needs	<p>What data is needed for quality assurance?</p> <p>What data is needed for traceability?</p> <p>What data is needed for decision making?</p> <p>What information is needed to capture the values identified in previous steps?</p> <p>Are we missing anything?</p>
8.	Define and/or develop an ontology	Described in D1.1
9.	Describe the data flow and connect to activities in the circular material path	Examples found In chapters 7.1 & 7.3
10.	Iterate step 2-10 if necessary	

Table 1. Key questions related to the steps to define Circular Value Flow Planning

Defining the physical steps: Once the material has been chosen and the boundaries are set, defining the physical flow is usually initiated by looking at the built environment. Usually, the physical material path ´s starting point is in the built environment, and, in the case of circular material paths, the path ends in the built environment

Figure 3 below shows a general material path for a circular material. This generalization is based on knowledge that has been gained through interviews and workshops discussing circularity and the requirements a manufacturing company has on the inbound material for their production.

Figure 3: A generic circular material path and possible data flow

Defining the data and information needs: One important part of the data collection is the inventory of the built environment, described further in chapter 3.2.2 Tools for defining data and information needs & data collection.

Define and/or develop an ontology: The data and information gathered along the circular material path will be shared among various stakeholders and integrated into

different processes across multiple organizations. To enable scalable and effective data sharing, it is essential to establish a common information model (an ontology) that ensures a shared understanding among all stakeholders. This approach is detailed in *Deliverable D1.1: An Ontology for Circular Management of Buildings*.

3.2. Tools and technologies

3.2.1. Tools for defining the physical steps

Desktop research

Desktop research is used to gather background information and identify existing knowledge, actors, and initiatives relevant to flat glass recycling and circular value flows. This method enables the systematic review of scientific publications, industry reports, policy documents, and online platforms.

Interviews

Interviews are used to collect insights from stakeholders across the flat glass value chain. This method captures practical knowledge, uncovers barriers and opportunities, and complements data gathered through desktop research and other sources.

Workshops

Workshops are used to validate findings, align perspectives among stakeholders, and co-develop potential solutions for circular flat glass flows. They facilitate knowledge exchange, strengthen collaboration, and support the integration of insights from interviews and research.

Digital whiteboards

Digital whiteboards are used to document insights, map processes, and visualize data collaboratively throughout this research. They support real-time co-creation during workshops and interviews and help structure complex information clearly.

3.2.2. Tools for defining data and information needs & data collection

Data needs to be generated and collected from the entire value chain and will be managed in the common platform, CP-IM using the ontology developed to enable scalable data sharing between different stakeholders.

Inventory of the material bank

Scalable data sharing between different stakeholders requires a comprehensive and accessible inventory of the material bank (all materials in the built environment). This inventory involves collecting data from the built environment to understand what materials are available for reuse or recycling. In the Reincarnate project, both digital and manual inventory methods have been tested to map the material stock embedded in the built environment.

External databases & APIs

To collect the data that is required for circular value flow planning different databases needs to be collected. External databases of interest can be those where instructions for dismantling are available. Examples of other data bases relevant in the Swedish context are: Boverket and Worldfavor. Sharing can occur in several ways, for example: by uploading data to the common platform, creating an API that retrieves information from an organization's internal database, or through other suitable integration methods

Point cloud data

Point cloud data, typically generated through 3D scanning technologies such as Laser, LiDAR or photogrammetry, can provide accurate spatial information about buildings and structures. Point cloud data can be regarded as a valuable source for assessing the physical state, dimensions, and potential for disassembly or reuse of materials. This type of data supports the identification of material quantities and locations, enabling more precise planning of circular material paths. The integration of point cloud data with other information sources enhances both the spatial and material resolution of the analysis.

BIM models

Building Information Models (BIM) can be used to structure and visualize data related to building components, materials, and systems. BIM models enable the integration of geometric, technical, and environmental data, providing a digital twin of the built asset. This approach supports the assessment of reuse potential, material composition, and lifecycle characteristics. By linking BIM models with other data sources, such as point clouds or external database, circular value flows can be planned and simulated with

greater accuracy and efficiency. BIM models can be used for quick generation of quantities and queries.

Non-destructive testing

Non-destructive testing (NDT) methods can be employed to assess the condition and integrity of building materials without causing damage. Techniques such as ground-penetrating radar, infrared thermography, and ultrasonic testing allow for the evaluation of structural elements and hidden defects. These methods are particularly valuable for determining the potential for reuse or recycling of materials in existing structures. NDT contributes to more informed decision-making in circular value flow planning by providing accurate, on-site data on material quality.

4. Use cases

4.1. Glass

Glass production is an energy-intensive industry that generates significant carbon emissions due to the high temperatures required to melt raw materials and the use of fossil fuels in traditional furnaces which aims to reduce its energy consumption. The EU is the world's biggest producer of glass, with a market share of around one-third of total world production within container glass (60% of output in tonnage), flat glass (about 30% in tonnage), and domestic glass, special glass, and reinforcement glass fibers¹⁹. In order to state the effective collection and reprocessing of glass schemes, it is crucial to have a better understanding of the existing circular economy principles within the alternative upcycling routes across the glass value chain. However, findings indicate that achieving the financial viability of material reuse can be challenging. Products made from reused materials can require substantial manufacturing processes and input of (costly) primary materials, while secondary material inputs may still generate substantial costs²⁰.

Flat glass, typically manufactured through the float process, is used extensively in the building sector for architectural glazing and structural applications. Global production

¹⁹ Glass. (n.d.). Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs. https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/sectors/raw-materials/related-industries/non-metallic-products-and-industries/glass_en

²⁰ Nußholz, J. L., Rasmussen, F. N., Whalen, K., & Plepys, A. (2020). Material reuse in buildings: Implications of a circular business model for sustainable value creation. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 245, 118546.

exceeds 100 million metric tons annually, with significant volumes becoming waste due to renovation, demolition, or glass defects during manufacturing. Despite its recyclability, only a small fraction of flat glass is reused in high-value applications. The majority is either downcycled into insulation products or disposed of in landfills. In contrast, the direct reuse of flat glass panels -maintaining their original form and function- could dramatically reduce the building sector's environmental footprint.

The current glass supply chain in Sweden and in the EU includes both recycling and downcycling routes, with the latter primarily involving the use of cullet in container glass and glass wool production. These applications represent common end-of-life destinations for glass that cannot meet the purity standards required for high-quality reuse. Beyond these, glass is also used as an alternative raw material in products such as concrete, filtration media, and glass ceramics, extending across various building-related subsectors. Figure 4 illustrates this alternative recovery and downcycling scenarios for end-of-life glass.

Figure 4: Alternative glass recovery scenarios for end-of-life management for downcycling applications (a high-resolution image can be found in appendix 3)

4.1.1. Recycling of flat glass

The main barrier to increasing post-consumer recycling rates lies in the ability to recover flat glass cullet that is sufficiently clean, uncontaminated, and cost-effective to process²¹. Float glass manufacturing demands extremely low levels of contamination, which poses a challenge for recycled sourced from CDW or post-consumer sources. Interestingly, CDW sites generally offer cullet with lower contamination risk compared to household glass waste, such as bottles and jars²². As a result, most contaminated glass cullet is diverted toward lower-value applications, especially in the container glass and glass wool industries.

Demand for glass cullet for glass wool production has increased over the last 20 years due to higher demand for insulation products that meet building energy performance targets. Glass wool production typically incorporates up to 80% of pre-and post-consumer cullet in new production by combining two types of recycled glass cullet (one from CRT and the other from soda-lime silicate glasses) with different foaming agents²³²⁴. Foam glass also uses both kinds of recycled glass cullet. Here the quality demands are even lower.

Beyond traditional recycling, glass waste can be downcycled into several valuable applications by replacing natural raw materials in industrial processes. For instance, finely ground glass cullet can be used as a partial substitute for cement in concrete, reducing both resource extraction and CO₂ emissions. In the production of glass ceramics, glass waste can replace key raw ingredients, contributing to more resource-efficient manufacturing. Additionally, in water filtration systems, glass particles have

²¹ Hartwell, R., Coult, G., & Overend, M. (2023). Mapping the flat glass value-chain: a material flow analysis and energy balance of UK production. *Glass Structures & Engineering*, 8(2), 167-192.

²² Rose, A., Sack, N., ift Rosenheim, Nothacker, K., Gassman, A., & Fraunhofer ISC. (2019). Recycling of flat glass in the building industry – Analysis of the current situation and derivation of recommendations for action. ift gemeinnützige Forschungs- und Entwicklungsgesellschaft mbH. https://www.irbnet.de/daten/kbf/kbf_e_F_3202.pdf

²³ Coult, G., & Hartwell, R. (2024). Returning glass to the supply chain. *The Structural Engineer: journal of the Institution of Structural Engineer*, 102(1), 40-42.

²⁴ Delbari, S. A., & Hof, L. A. (2024). Glass waste circular economy-Advancing to high-value glass sheets recovery using industry 4.0 and 5.0 technologies. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 142629.

demonstrated potential as a replacement for silica sand in rapid filtration processes²⁵. These downcycling pathways offer environmental benefits beyond resource substitution. They enable the immobilization and stabilization of potentially hazardous elements present in certain types of glass waste, reducing the risk of environmental contamination during disposal or further use.

4.1.1.1 Physical flow

The main features of the material path will be similar in every EU country, but the details will differ from country to country. In this chapter the Swedish process is described.

Figure 5 below presents the material path of flat glass to flat glass and the side streams of material that can be used in other contexts. The residue from the quality assurance, highlighted in Figure 22 is used as use case for the concrete binder described in chapter 4.2.

Figure 5: The circular flow from flat glass to flat glass

²⁵ Delbari, S. A., & Hof, L. A. (2024). Glass waste circular economy-Advancing to high-value glass sheets recovery using industry 4.0 and 5.0 technologies. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 142629.

Swedish buildings that make up the contextual material bank contain much glass. Deloitte estimated that a total of 35 000-ton flat glass is removed in Sweden every year²⁶. An inventory of the glass in the building is necessary as not all types can be recycled into raw material for new window glass production. Some fractions are not possible to recycle or reuse at all and some are identified as hazardous material.

Raw materials for new flat glass production have very high demands on quality set by flat glass producers. Consequently, it is not possible to crush the whole window in a container since the risk of contamination, and thus loss of quality, is high. The windows need to be removed intact from the building and loaded on pallets. The pallets are then transported to the nearest recycling site.

Transportation is necessary for circular solutions, and it is important to optimize them due to the emissions, extra work hours and thus costs connected to transportation. In the case of a window, the frame needs to be removed as soon as possible. The process used in this project includes a pre-treatment process where the frame is removed and a glass fraction achieved through crushing. Right now, there are 5 such pre-treatment plants available across the country and many recycling sites feed each pre-treatment plant with windows.

After pre-treatment, the cullet usually contains too many contaminations, i.e. wood, putty and metals. These contaminations are removed in an optical sorting process. Since there is just one such quality assurance plant in Sweden, the cullet from the pre-treatment plants is shipped to the quality assurance plant in clean containers or vascular depending on the transportation distance.

There is an EU end of waste, EoW, criteria for glass cullet. The quality assurance plant full fills these and the outcome is a raw material suitable for float glass production. There is no flat glass production plant in Sweden, and the cullet must be exported. The transformation of waste into raw materials simplifies the export process. Many float glass plants are accessible by railroad and in the future, there might be a switch to railroad

²⁶ Hestin, M., de Veron, S., & Burgos, S. (2016). *Economic study on recycling of building glass in Europe*. Deloitte Sustainability. <https://www.glassforeurope.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/04/Economic-study-on-recycling-of-building-glass-in-Europe-Deloitte.pdf>

transports. New flat glass is produced and delivered to window production industries creating new windows closing the circular loop.

Melting cullet to produce new window glass saves primary raw materials, energy and has a significant impact on the carbon dioxide footprint. 1 kg of glass produced from raw materials need 1,2 kg primary raw materials while 1 kg cullet is enough. It is easier to melt cullet, and the amount of energy needed is 30% less than when primary raw materials are used. The total CO₂-footpring is twice as large for primary raw materials than when cullet is used. Thus, the CO₂ savings are larger that the transportations performed during the recycling process.

4.1.1.2 Data flow

The data required to circular flat glass to flat glass is determined by requirements from the value chain related to quality assurance and estimating volumes. The quality assurance assures that the recycled cullet meets the requirements for flat glass production while data to estimate and verify volumes is important to plan production and understand the feedstock.

Data collection begins with a comprehensive inventory of the built environment, encompassing the physical structure and associated facility documentation, such as original construction records and renovation histories.

This inventory data is used to evaluate each batch of flat glass for suitability in high-quality recycling, potential downgrading or detoxification, or, where necessary, final disposal (See chapter 7.1 Value flow 1: Upstream inventory of material bank for further explanation).

Accurate inventory data also enables volume estimates for flat glass that can re-enter the closed material loop versus quantities destined for lower-value applications or landfill. Moreover, making this information accessible to all stakeholders throughout the value flow is essential for informed decision-making and data verification. In the absence of reliable inventory data, flat glass cannot be assured for quality-controlled recycling and is ultimately diverted to landfill.

Data collection from the treatment process and quality assurance is important to verify the quality and get numbers on how much of the windows sent to flat glass recycling that ends up as an EoW product: the recycled cullet. These numbers also show how efficient the process is and makes it possible to estimate how big volumes of EoW product that is produced from a volume of windows.

The data on the amount of cullet sent to flat glass production is also data that is reported back to the facility owner, sending these specific windows to flat glass recycling, how much CO₂ is saved and how much virgin resources that has been replaced with recycled cullet.

The data from the pretreatment and quality assurance proceed are shared with the producer of the flat glass to add specific data to the produced flat glass. The amount of recycled cullet is important data for the flat glass producer to communicate and share with the manufacturer of windows, who uses flat glass with recycled content.

4.1.2. Downgrading of flat glass

The primary focus is always circular solutions where no downgrading is created. However, even though glass can be recycled infinite times in theory, it is not possible to recycle all glass to cullet for new float glass production due to realities in production. For example, there are tests with recycling laminated glass to cullet for new float glass production, but we have not come that far in Sweden yet, so laminated glass is downgraded to glass wool. There is also a fraction less than 8 mm which is a residue from the quality assurance process. This fraction is too small to be sorted in the optical sorter and is thus not recycled to flat glass. The residue consists of glass but also some wood and putty remain. It is approximately 5% of the through put of the process. This fraction is used in the SLAMD demonstration.

4.1.3. Reuse of flat glass

Alternative options for material efficiency include the direct reuse of the glass panel itself, a promising approach in the industry. This method, rather than returning the glass as a bulk material for recycling, utilizes the embodied carbon for a longer time and significantly reduces Primary Application Energy (PAE) losses by avoiding the need for

remelting cullet and energy-intensive secondary processing methods^{27,28}. The reuse approach, though in its infancy, holds immense potential. Valuable approaches for reducing energy input will need to understand better the feasibility of facilitating flat glass reuse since this eliminates the need for remelting; optimize procurement routes for primary raw materials, e.g., sourcing, processing, and transportation; and increase the awareness and availability of secondary processing methods that provide sufficient functional performance at minimal environmental cost²⁹.

Furthermore, after investigation and cleaning, this reusable flat glass can be used for refurbishing and remanufacturing, such as upgrading single-glazed windows to double- or triple-glazed ones. Ones require little adjustment to reuse in the building and can be repaired. In the literature, windows reduce energy consumption, carbon emissions, and waste while maintaining building value. This can be achieved by upcycling the window parts or components by replacing single-glazed windows with double or triple-glazed ones, significantly saving energy. The outer panes in a triple insulating unit are preferable coated to achieve the highest possible savings. The middle pane can be uncoated, and this is the most suitable pane for reused glass.

²⁷ Hartwell, R., Coult, G., & Overend, M. (2023). Mapping the flat glass value-chain: a material flow analysis and energy balance of UK production. *Glass Structures & Engineering*, 8(2), 167-192.

²⁸ Coult, G., & Hartwell, R. (2024). Returning glass to the supply chain. *The Structural Engineer: journal of the Institution of Structural Engineer*, 102(1), 40-42.

²⁹ Hartwell, R., Coult, G., & Overend, M. (2023). Mapping the flat glass value-chain: a material flow analysis and energy balance of UK production. *Glass Structures & Engineering*, 8(2), 167-192.

Figure 6: Alternative glass recovery scenarios for reuse, repair, refurbishment, and remanufacturing (See appendix V for high resolution image)

The following section explores the potential for reusing flat glass in the building market, examining technical, regulatory, economic, and environmental dimensions from a German perspective.

Approximately 1.67 million tons of flat glass are produced in Germany each year for use in building applications. During the same period, approximately 521,000 tons of cullet are generated. About two-thirds of this comes from building demolitions (post-consumer), while the remaining third reaches the recycler after further processing (pre-consumer). The flat glass industry faces a price problem. Only 101,000 tons (19%) make it from the recycler back to the flat glass manufacturers, following a modern circular economy model. One reason for this is that the quality standards to produce

architectural glass are particularly high. Even the slightest contamination of the cullet would make it impossible to use in modern float glass production. The systems are extremely sensitive to material changes and, in an emergency, must be recalibrated, which can cause months of production downtime. The second, and equally important, reason is that float glass prices have been low for decades. The container glass industry can simply pay higher prices for cullet and, at the same time, is less demanding when it comes to cullet quality. Therefore, a significantly larger proportion, namely 45% of the total, goes into the production of container glass, which represents downcycling. A further 32%, also downcycled, goes into the production of glass wool and other mineral building materials. And 4% of the cullet still ends up in landfills. The biggest obstacle to increasing the cullet share in the flat glass industry, however, is that, at 521,000 tons annually, there is not enough cullet for all industries. Unlike beverage bottles, flat glass is not a fast-moving commodity – it remains in windows and facades for decades. The flat glass industry cannot win the competition for cullet due to the low prices for basic glass.

4.1.3.1 Viability of reuse

Technical Viability of Reuse

Glass panels can be reused if they retain structural integrity and meet current safety and thermal performance standards. Furthermore, the second life transformation has additional demands related to the next life demands. Challenges include:

- Damage during removal
- Contamination (putty, sealants)
- Mismatch with current building regulations
- Need for coated glass

Processing and Logistics

Reuse requires careful deconstruction, storage, and reinstallation. Systems for labelling, tracking, and grading reused glass are underdeveloped. At the same time, a secondary processing is energy intensive and requests special logistics.

Economic Feasibility

While reused glass may be cheaper than new glass in raw cost, processing and

transport costs can offset savings. Incentives and standardization are needed to make reuse economically competitive.

Case Studies and Emerging Practices

Several pilot projects and start-ups across Europe and North America are testing reuse strategies e.g.:

- Rotor Deconstruction (Belgium) collects and resells deconstructed glass from buildings.
- Re-Glaze (UK) develops systems to retrofit old glass into modern framing solutions.
- Urban Mining concepts integrate reused glass into design from the outset.

These examples show that reuse is possible but currently niche and reliant on innovative business models.

4.2. Recycled concrete fines

Within the context of the SLAMD-demo Ragn-Sells aims to also explore the possibility of using concrete fines from mixed construction and demolition waste to produce binder for concrete. The recycled concrete would comprise of structural concrete debris, pavement fragments, and masonry residues from various demolition projects. This heterogeneous source material inherently contains diverse concrete types with varying original mix designs (e.g., water-cement ratios, cement types, aggregate mineralogy), which would result in fluctuations in the adhered mortar content and residual hydration products within the fines. Exploring how and if such material could with the help of SLAMD derive a less CO₂ taxing concrete binder compared to virgin binder is something that will be explored within the context of SLAMD. For such material to be useful, a preliminary sorting to segregate hazardous and non-hazardous fractions would be needed. Additionally standard protocols for detecting contaminants like asbestos or organic pollutants will be used and possibly enhanced quality control measures such as X-ray fluorescence (XRF) analysis may be used. Only non-hazardous, low-contaminant batches would be selected for further processing, ensuring compliance with EN 12620 standards for concrete reuse.

5. BIM for circular value flow planning

To achieve the EU's goal of climate neutrality by 2050 and the global goals (goal 13 combat climate change) and, according to the Paris Agreement, limit global warming to 1.5 degrees, a more careful use of the Earth's resources is required. With increased urbanization and thus a greater need for resources, better planning is needed, as described in Chapter 2.1 Challenges in Reuse and Recycling.

3D modelling with building information modelling (BIM), is standard for modern design and project management and holds huge possibilities for multiple and generative applications. Since BIM today is widely used in the construction sector, we see it as a futureproof format that has the potential to evolve over time. The construction industry is rapidly evolving with digitalisation and the need for structured ways of working, including describing BIM objects, are crucial. We believe that existing BIM models can be enriched with data that holds information for recycling and reuse purposes in order to simplify recycling or reuse once the product or building has reached end of life.

The innovation BIM for circular flow planning (BIM-CVFP) builds on the concept of Circular value flow planning, which aims at enabling better planning of material paths as described in chapter 2.3, using a BIM model as the facilitator of data collected from the built environment. The collected data is stored in different BIM objects and the data is structured according to an ontology.

By systematically building up ontologies, see Deliverable 1.1, for the circular economy based on different materials and their specific functions, processes and properties, a digital readable format is created, a format that is neutral that can be read and integrated by different software which are compatible with IFC format. BIM-CVFP reads or adds data to the specific BIM objects and based on the data, in combination with a material specific ontology, it gives a recommendation on the most suitable handling, recycling route, for the material. The recommendation can be customised based on the parameters chosen by the user, for example, cost or climate impact. The methodology enables a system to provide tailored recommendations based on material-specific information embedded in a BIM model. By adhering to a standardized structure and utilizing a template file with shared parameters, the BIM model is

equipped with predefined fields that facilitate data input and consistency. These shared parameters act as placeholders, allowing inventory data such as material types, quantities, and conditions, to be imported and organized systematically within the model. This structured approach ensures that relevant information is accurately linked to the corresponding building elements, supporting reliable decision-making for reuse and recycling strategies.

BIM models can store or link large amount of data to a specific object within the BIM models. A BIM model can be very complex and data heavy depending on the level of detail (LOD). When developing an ontology, it has been identified what data the model should contain related to a specific material. The predefined structure makes it possible to collect data for many different materials using the same BIM model as facilitator. This is a scalable and efficient way of enabling more materials from the built environment to be circularized.

The innovation BIM for Circular value flow planning will be demonstrated in 2 demonstrations. Demo 1: *Value flow 1 – Upstream inventory of the material bank* and Demo 3: *Value flow 3: Flat glass to flat glass*. These value flows will be demonstrated in WP5 and are further described in chapter 7. Circular value flows for flat glass. The innovation aims to create values and data for decisions for several actors in the value chain. For example; the real estate owner can get specific data on how much of their building that has been sent to high quality recycling and how much CO2 this saves; the waste management company gets data on the feedstock (the built environment) and how much recycled material this will generate; the manufacturing company get data on how much material that is available. These are examples of the value which can be created by BIM for Circular value flow planning.

With BIM-CVFP we aim to increase the materials from the built environment to be circular, staying in the loop. By enriching BIM models with additional data facilitating for reuse or recycling, the models will serve a circular purpose that enables materials to be used in the most resource efficient way possible.

6. CP-IM Integration and API Connections

6.1. CP-IM & Data Flow

The CP-IM platform provides centralized and structured management of two main categories of flows: data flow and material path. The data flow encompasses real-time and historical sensor data collected through the Mainflux IoT platform. It integrates information from multiple sources, including IoT sensors for environmental conditions, structural monitoring, industrial scales, robotic sorting systems, and asset inspection, as well as external databases from waste management and product lifecycle management systems. Figure 7 gives an overview of the different components.

Figure 7: The overview of modules in CP-IM (See appendix VI for high resolution)

6.2. BIM & Data Flow

Complementary to the IoT data, BIM models stored and managed in the RE Suite provide detailed digital representations of buildings, capturing precise information about building elements, products, and materials. These models serve as reference points that link physical components (e.g., windows, doors, concrete elements, and glass façades) with their static attributes, real-time status, sensor measurements, and historic

Despite their widespread adoption in the architecture, engineering, and construction industries, BIM models often fall short of realizing their full potential. One of the main challenges is that these models are typically developed for design and construction purposes and tend to become static or underutilized during the operational phase of a building. They often lack comprehensive, structured information about materials, components, and their interrelations—limiting their usefulness for tasks such as renovation planning, resource recovery, or lifecycle analysis. Moreover, inconsistencies in how models are developed, and the use of proprietary formats further hinder data reuse and interoperability. To address these issues, BIM models need to be semantically enriched with structured, contextual data that reflects the actual composition and potential of the built environment. To facilitate decision-making, the BIM model can be enriched with relevant data using the ontology-based methodology proposed in D1.1. Once the BIM model is enriched with the required data, various queries can be generated to quickly assess the destination of materials or components. An example of such an application has been implemented in the CP-IM.

6.3. Implementation in CP-IM

The implementation of circular value flow planning within CP-IM is supported by a modular architecture that enables integration of diverse data sources and tools. As shown in Figure 8, the system consists of interconnected modules that collectively support the extraction, enrichment, querying, and visualization of building and material data. This includes using IFC-based BIM models via the RE Suite, linking them to relevant external data sources (e.g., material databases, LCA resources), and enriching them with ontologically structured metadata as proposed in D1.1. The enrichment process enables semantic understanding of components and their properties, facilitating automated reasoning and decision-making. To operationalize enriched BIM data, the system incorporates a query engine that interprets user-defined logic and navigates the IFC model structure accordingly. This logic is constructed via a graphical user interface that allows users to build queries using logical operators, conditions, and hierarchical relationships among building components. The engine then traverses the IFC element tree and returns relevant matches, which are visualized in a BIM viewer and optionally exported. The platform also maintains links to external knowledge sources, such as classification rules (e.g., recyclability conditions), which are used to automate the categorization of materials in context-specific workflows. This integration enables the

identification of circular potentials across multiple value flows—from reuse and recycling to downcycling and disposal—based on both static and dynamic criteria.

Figure 8: The overview of modules and their interactions

6.3.1. IFC-based application for circular value flow decision making

As an open standard, IFC is designed to facilitate the seamless exchange of building information among stakeholders. Once an ifc file is enriched with relevant data, querying circularity aspects becomes equivalent to querying IFC-defined properties and their values. For example, if it is known that wired glass is non-recyclable, this knowledge can be operationalized through IFC queries: any window elements in an IFC model with the property `IsWired` set to `true` within the property set `PSet_DoorWindowGlazing` can be automatically flagged and excluded from recyclable material paths. Given a sufficiently enriched IFC model, a predefined set of queries can automatically classify flat glass elements in a building into categories such as recyclable, downcyclable, or destined for landfill, thereby supporting data-driven circularity assessments.

6.3.2. Queries

The power of a query engine depends on the complexity and flexibility of the queries it supports. The queries are defined based on the decision making processes defined for each value flow. The flat-glass categorization example reveals several key requirements for such a query engine:

- A query should return a list of matching IFC elements.
- A match is defined as satisfying a binary expression tree of logical conditions.

- A condition can be of two types:
 - **Property-based condition**, defined as a triple: `[identifier] [operator] [value]`.
 - Identifiers must correspond to property or argument names, optionally scoped to a specific property set (PSet).
 - Supported operators include:
 - Binary: equals, not equals, greater than, greater than or equal, less than, less than or equal, partial string match.
 - Unary: exists, not exists (these do not require a value).
 - **Relational condition** involving another element, expressed as a nested binary expression tree.
 - Supported relations include: parent, child, ancestor, descendant.
- Multiple conditions can be combined using logical operators: AND, OR.
- The **precedence** of logical operators is handled through the grouping of conditions within the binary decision tree.

6.3.3. LCA data base

To calculate the global warming potential in CO₂ equivalent (CO₂e) requires knowledge of the quantity of material present in a building or component and the amount of CO₂ equivalent per quantity of material for the destined recycling strategy. The former can be extracted from the BIM model through queries (Figure 9). The latter requires a sufficiently populated material database.

The Swedish National Board of Housing, Building and Planning, Boverket, offers a climate database (Klimatdatabas) that contains such values. The database contains, for example, conservative and typical values for climate impact per quantity of material over various categories for hundreds of materials. The database is periodically updated with a rough frequency of every 6 months and offers an API³⁰ for data extraction in an automated and machine-readable format.

³⁰ Boverket. (2024). *API för Klimatdatabas* [API for Climate Database]. <https://www.boverket.se/sv/om-boverket/publicerat-av-boverket/oppna-data/boverkets-klimatdatabas>

The API offers a single endpoint to retrieve all data at once. It does not offer a calculation endpoint or search functionality to retrieve just the required data. With these constraints and given the infrequent updates of the database content it is most efficient to retain a local copy of the data in the CP-IM and use that for calculations. A separate import process can refresh the local copy at need without impacting the user experience. Data in the Boverket database is available in Swedish and English. It contains, among other things:

- material descriptions,
- assessment constraints and guidelines,
- conversion factors (e.g. between volume and mass, if applicable)
- global warming potential for various recycling categories

Figure 9: Connection between CP-IM and Boverket Klimatdatabas

6.3.4. Search engine

RE Suite, the foundation for CP-IM, utilizes the IFCEngine by RDF to interact with IFC files and data. The IFCEngine API supports iteration over elements, arguments, and properties and enables value extraction. An algorithm performs a Depth First Search (DFS) traversal through the IFC model's element-property tree. For each IFC element, the engine evaluates query conditions and applies recursion where relational conditions are present.

6.3.5. Graphical User Interface

The query functionality is integrated into the CP-IM's existing BIM viewer. This viewer supports a repository of IFC files, 3D visualization, and full model and property navigation.

Users can explore actual IFC files to inspect property values, which assists in defining meaningful queries.

The GUI consists of a central BIM viewer with a query panel accessible via a dedicated button (see Figure 10). This side panel includes three main components:

- Query selection panel (top right): Start a new query or select an existing one.
- Query definition panel (middle right): Define logical groups and conditions using a flexible user interface.
- Result panel (bottom right): View matched element names and GUIDs, highlighted in the 3D viewer. Export results as .csv.

Figure 10: IFC Query Graphical User Interface (GUI)

Within the definition panel, users can add conditions and groups (as shown in Figure 11). Each group can be set to match all (AND) or any (OR) of its conditions, which can target either the object itself or a related element (e.g., ancestor). Conditions follow a triple format, such as Pset_WallCommon.IsExternal equals true, with identifiers and values entered as free text and operators chosen from a dropdown. Each group and condition can be removed individually.

This interface allows flexible and powerful configuration of queries, enabling users to perform complex searches to support circularity assessments and material classification.

Figure 11: Query definition panel

7. Circular value flows for flat glass

In the previous chapters, we introduced the concept of circular value flow planning and proposed a methodology for mapping such processes. We then focused on flat glass as a use case and examined its potential end-of-life destinations. In this chapter, we will elaborate on four distinct value flows specific to the flat glass use case.

A circular material path ensures that materials retain their original quality as they move through each step of the value chain. In this case, the “flat glass to flat glass” recycling process was co-developed by Ragn-Sells and Saint-Gobain (the window producer) to satisfy the methodological requirements outlined above. A closed-closing recycling workflow is now established that confirms each batch of reclaimed glass meets stringent quality criteria before re-entry into production.

The “flat glass to flat glass” cycle serves as the foundational circular material path underpinning all value flows described in this deliverable. It begins with quality-assured flat glass residues, for which comprehensive data are collected to determine the appropriate trajectory (full recycling, downgrading, landfill, or specialized treatment). This data-driven approach guarantees that only glass conforming to circular recycling standards re-enters the material loop.

The steps of the physical flow to recycle flat glass to flat glass can be found in Figure 5.

Limitations and assumptions that have been considered for this study are:

- Only consider flat glass to flat glass recycling

- No side streams of material, except residue that will be used in the SLAMD value flow.
- Looking at the simplest pretreatment process, when the pretreatment and quality assurance is placed at the same site.
- Only identifying and including key actors.

The data and actors identified in this study are those necessary to enable an effective flat glass recycling process. The value generated through this system includes the provision of recycled raw materials, reduced reliance on virgin resources, and decreased CO₂ emissions. Based on the process described in Figure 5, specific actors, as well as the required data inputs and expected outputs, have been mapped for each step. This mapping provides a foundation for understanding how information flows and responsibilities are distributed throughout the recycling chain, supporting the development of a functional and scalable circular system for flat glass.

Step 1: Window in building – the built environment

Step	Stakeholder	Responsibility	Input	Output
1: The built environment : ie. Window in building	Facility owner	Initiate construction project (mandate to pay for recycling of windows), share relevant data and information with project	CO2-savings (CO2 data), inventory data, agreement information	location, building data
1: The built environment : ie. Window in building	Inventory person	Inventory of the built environment, investigate hazardous waste	Building data to plan inventory (incl. environmental investigation)	Inventory data
1: The built environment : ie. Window in building	Receiver of flat glass/manufacturer of flat glass cullet	Ensuring requirements for flat glass inventory is received by inventory	Inventory data to estimate volumes	Requirements for handling of windows to enable flat glass recycling,

		person, putting up agreement with facility owner		agreement information with facility owner
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Step 2: Dismantling window

Step	Stakeholder	Responsibility	Input	Output
2: Dismantling window	Dismantler, construction worker	Dismantling, sorting and packaging of windows on load carriers, notifies transporter when to collect load carriers	Requirements for handling windows to enable flat glass recycling	deviations, notification to collect load carriers
2: Dismantling window	Transporter	Collecting load carriers with windows, transportation to treatment site, control of goods	Notification to collect orders, location	Order number, Weight on windows, deviations data, Arrival at treatment site

Step 3: Pretreatment process

Step	Stakeholder	Responsibility	Input	Output
3: Pretreatment process	Pretreatment operator	Separating glass from frame, deviation control, packaging of pretreated cullet	Order number	Weight glass cullet from pretreatment, pretreatment batch number, weight side streams (frames, metals etc), deviation data

Step 4: Quality assurance

Step	Stakeholder	Responsibility	Input	Output
4: Quality assurance	Quality assurance operator	Quality assuring the glass cullet from	weight on glass cullet from	Weight on quality assured cullet

		pretreatment process	pretreatment, pretreatment batch number	(EoW product), weight on residue, EoW batch number, deviation data
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Step 5: Flat glass production with recycled cullet

Step	Stakeholder	Responsibility	Input	Output
5: Flat glass production with recycled cullet	Production planner	Mixing the recycled, quality assured, cullet for right proportions	EoW batch number, Weight on quality assured cullet: the End of Waste product	Amount of flat glass produced with recycled cullet, product data flat glass

Step 6: Processing flat glass

Step	Stakeholder	Responsibility	Input	Output
6: Processing flat glass	Glass processor	Processing flat glass based on market demands and requirements	Amount of flat glass produced with recycled cullet, product data	Product data processed glass

Step 7: Window manufacturing

Step	Stakeholder	Responsibility	Input	Output
7: Window manufacturing	Window manufacturer	Manufacturing of new windows based on market demands and requirements	Product data from glass processor and flat glass producer	Product data Window

7.1. Value flow 1: Upstream inventory of material bank

Figure 12: The physical flow and focus of the first demonstration

The first demonstration aims at enabling high quality recycling and reuse as well as evaluating different inventory methods. This will be done by collecting data for recycling using different methods such as 3D scanning, manual inventory and inventory using digital tools. The collected data will be connected to the ontology in *D1.1 An ontology for circular management of buildings*. The demo also aims to exploring ways of connecting collected inventory data to the CP-IM platform.

In the inventory phase, data is collected to assess which of the following routes the material can take:

- Recycling w/o downgrading Scenario - Green
- Recycling Downgrading Scenario - Blue (Laminated)
- Landfill with further assessment - Red
- Landfill Scenario - Red
- Combustion Scenario - Red
- Special treatment Scenario - Red
- Hazardous Waste - Black

The colour is how the windows are labelled in the physical flow. Once the colour is determined, the inventory step of the demonstration is finished.

7.1.1. Tools to be tested

Boverket CO2 templates

In order to add CO2 information to the flat glass the CO2 estimates from the Swedish National Board of Housing, Building and Planning for steps A1-A5 in the lifecycle of a product will be imported to the CP-IM platform.

Ragn-Sells ERP and CRM systems

As part of the demonstration, we aim to connect relevant parts of Ragn-Sells ERP and CRM systems to the CP-IM platform in order to populate the flat glass data with relevant data points.

Point cloud

One of the most crucial parts of the innovation is the generation of point cloud data, here we see a huge value potential by adding relevant information in an early stage. The digital representation from the point cloud does not only give measurable geometry but also an updated representation of a building as it is in that given time.

To get the point cloud for the demonstration we use a mobile lidar scanner Naavis VLX3, this hardware is more time efficient than traditional terrestrial laser scanners and almost the same accuracy. Another reason for choosing Naavis VLX is the cloud bases viewer Ivion Core that Naavis provides. Ivion Core let you measure, add Points of interest (POI), crop and share data in a user-friendly way without the need for specific point cloud software. For the more advanced usability and result point cloud software is still recommended, but for adding relevant information in geographical points and coordinates by none experts have Ivion Core more than enough functionalities for any expected result.

Figure 13: Example of Naavis VLX3 hardware and the Ivion Core software

Inventory devices

In the demonstration we will assess different mobile devices and how we can add data in Ivion Core out in the buildings-sight in a user-friendly and time efficient way. We think that the mobility and possibility to take pictures in the field is the best way to document quality assured data without spending too much time and with a low margin of human errors. In the assessment we will try a computer with a touch screen, two different tablets and mobile phones.

Figure 14: Example of how an inventory could look like in practice

Excel templates

As a comparison we will also try the traditional way of inventory by using Excel templates to fill in the measurements and types of different building components. We will measure time consumption and data accuracy, but also the simplicity of exporting data to CP-IM.

Non-destructive testing

The digital inventory will be made using the non-destructive tool GlassBuddy (Figure 15) developed by Bohle. The tool will be used to analyse glass thickness, pane structure, coatings and the position of the window. For more information about the tool see:

<https://www.bohle.com/se-EN/GlassBuddy-Plus/BO5164755#bohle-anchor-BohleTheme.productdetail.titlesupply>

Figure 15: The GlassBuddy used for non-destructive testing

7.1.2. Data flow hypothesis

For the data flow from inventory to CP-IM we have derived 4 different methods, each motivating its own data flow hypothesis. All the hypotheses focus on enabling recycling of flat glass to flat glass, consequently there is no materialized flow for reuse. Much of the general structure of all the data flow hypothesis are based on the ontology presented in D1.1. Specifically, Table 7: The inference rules table for flat glass recycling. Additionally, all the data flow hypothesis are based on the assumptions that there is a graphical interface through which the user can interact with the data flow. The key interaction points, which function as input to the flow to move in one or the other direction, are marked as grey diamonds in Figure 18. There is a legend for the different symbols used in the data flow visualizations in Figure 16. Finally, each data flow hypothesis shows what component in CP-IM we think would host the data, the flow and interaction with the user. Consequently, the different components of the data flow hypothesis are connected to the various parts of the CP-IM platform based on the visualization from Figure 7.

Essential flowchart symbols

Terminal

Marks the beginning or end of a process. Think of it as a "Start" or "Finish" sign in a race.

Process step

The main object in a diagram. It represents an action or a step in a process.

Decision

This is the "fork in the road." It represents a point where a decision needs to be made.

Other useful symbols

Data input or output

Indicates information going in or out of a process. For example: data entry, a report generation, etc.

Predefined process

Represents steps defined elsewhere, like saying "Refer to recipe" instead of listing baking steps.

Database

This is where the process stores information, like a "storage room" for data.

Document

This shape symbolizes a document or report in the process, something you might print or save.

Multiple documents

Just like the single document, but it's used when there are multiple documents involved.

Preparation

A step that prepares for the next part of the process, like preheating an oven before baking.

Manual input

A step that prepares for the next part of the process, like preheating an oven before baking.

Figure 16: Legend for reading the data flow hypothesis

Inference Rules

<p>Let building be an IFCBuilding Let project be an IFCProject Let windowType be an IFCWindowType Let Object.property denote attribute 'property' in IFCObject 'Object'</p>	
<p>1. If building.YearOfConstruction or if windowType.Pset_ManufacturerTypeInfoomation.ProductionYear<=2001 then "PCB is likely in the window insulating unit" :: "PCB is likely in the window putty" then Combustion Scenario</p>	<p>Polychlorinated biphenyls are highly carcinogenic chemical compounds, formerly used in industrial and consumer products, whose production was banned in the United States by the Toxic Substances Control Act in 1976 and internationally by the Stockholm Convention on Persistent Organic Pollutants in 2001¹⁵. If CombustionScenario is observed then the glass can only be used for combustion (burning or incinerating a material, typically to release energy or dispose of waste).</p>
<p>2. If building.YearOfConstruction or if windowType.Pset_ManufacturerTypeInfoomation.ProductionYear<=2005 then "Asbestos" is likely in the window putty" :: "Asbestos is likely in the window putty" then Landfill Scenario</p>	<p>As of 1 July 1993 individuals and businesses in the Netherlands are not allowed to use, reuse, store, sell, import, repurpose, treat or give away asbestos. In 2005 a similar ban was introduced across the entire European Union.</p>
<p>3. If windowType.PartitioningType== 'Georgian bar' then Recycling Without Downgrading Scenario</p>	<p>This enumeration [PartitioningType] defines the basic configuration of the window type in terms of the number of window panels and the subdivision of the total window as shown here. It is also possible to add user defined types. This is helpful when specific types are common in a country and might have specific implication for the end life scenario. Similarly a user can indicate that it is a "connected" type of window which is common in Nordic countries.</p>
<p>4. If windowType.Pset_WindowCommon.IntegratedBlind ==True then Recycling Without Downgrading Scenario</p>	<p>Interstitial blinds or integrated blinds are high quality aluminum Venetian blinds in between two panes</p>

5. <i>If windowType.Pset_DoorWindowGlazing.IsLaminated ==True then Recycling Downgrading Scenario</i>	Currently laminated glass is not introduced into the glass furnace. When removing the laminate it is hard to maintain the quality
6. <i>If windowType.Pset_DoorWindowGlazing.IsTempered ==True then Recycling without Downgrading, Special Treatment scenario</i>	Tempered glass breaks into small pieces posing challenges to ensure quality. Thus, special treatment is needed.
7. <i>If windowType.Pset_DoorWindowGlazing.IsWired ==True then Landfill</i>	It is not possible to recycled wired glass.
8. <i>If windowType.Pset_DoorWindowGlazing.IsFilmed <= 0.25mm then Recycling Without Downgrading Scenario;if higher or none then Recycling Downgrading Scenario</i>	A thin film can be accepted into the glass furnace but a film thicker than 0.25mm is treated as laminated glass.
9. <i>If windowType.Pset_DoorWindowGlazing.GlassColor is not null then Recycling Downgrading Scenario</i>	The enamel will interfere with the quality and depending on the composition it might or might not be able to use for glass wool. If it is not possible to use for glass wool landfill is the most likely scenario.
10. <i>If windowType.Pset_DoorWindowGlazing.IsEnamelled ==True then Recycling, Downgrading or Landfill Scenario with further assessment of Enamel composition</i>	The recycling, downcycling, or disposal of glass depends on the composition of the enamel. If the enamel contains heavy metals beyond a certain threshold, the glass must be sent to a landfill. However, if the enamel contains a low amount or no heavy metals, the glass can be considered for recycling with downgrading. In cases where the glass contains substances that may pose harm or become explosive during the recycling process, it is also directed to a landfill. Therefore, the choice of recycling method is contingent on the enamel's composition, and it may require destructive or other tests to confirm its content
11. <i>If windowType.Pset_DoorWindowGlazing.IsPatterned ==True then Recycling or Downgrading Scenario</i>	Small quantities of patterned glass can undergo a recycling process, leading to the upcycling of the material into flat glass. However, when dealing with larger volumes, the upcycling process may not be feasible, and instead, the glass will be downgraded. The decision between upcycling and downgrading is contingent on the volume at hand, necessitating case-by-case evaluation.

Figure 17: Table 7: The inference rules table for flat glass recycling (D1.1)

Method 1a

The first method (1a) assumes that:

- there is no BIM model available
- 3D scanning of the project can be made
- Inventory can be done using a direct interface to REsuite
- BIM objects can be created based on the collected information from the inventory

- there is a BIM model available
- Inventory is done manually
- The available BIM model is enriched with inventory data.

Figure 20: Data flow hypothesis for method 2 (for high resolution image see URL in appendix 1)

The main difference between method 2 and the previous methods is that we assume that a BIM model is available. Consequently, we would need some way of checking the BIM model if the necessary datapoints are available and ensure that the version of the BIM model with the necessary datapoints is converted to an IFC file. If there are not available data points, these can be provided through the manual inventory which is delivered through an import of a data carrier (ie: CSV file) into the IoT platform directly.

Method 3

In testing method 3 we assume:

- there is no BIM model available
- Inventory is done manually

- There is a manual conversion of window information to IFC objects.

Figure 21: Data flow hypothesis for method 3 (for high resolution image see URL in appendix 1)

In this method there is no IFC imported to CP-IM. That is the core characteristics of the method compared to the other ones.

7.1.3. Summary of hypothesis to evaluate in demonstration 1

- An inventory together with a 3D scanning is a more efficient way of making inventories of the built environment and gives higher accuracy.
- It is more time efficient to do an inventory using CP-IM compared to a manual inventory.
- A scanning can facilitate all relevant geometries and information to create a BIM model based on the scanning.
- Can the data points collected in the inventory be shared in a scalable way using the CP-IM platform?

7.2. Value flow 2: SLAMD

SLAMD (Sequential Learning App for Materials Discovery) is an AI-driven software platform developed as part of the Reincarnate Project (for more details compare Deliverable 3.4) to accelerate the discovery of sustainable, more secondary raw material-based building materials. It integrates advanced inverse design methodologies with a digital twin of the laboratory to enable efficient exploration and optimization of complex material formulations, especially in data-scarce environments^{31,32}

The SLAMD platform consists of two core components:

1. **Digital Lab:**

This module allows users to define and manage materials, processes, and associated ecological and economic impacts. Users define base materials (e.g., recycled glass fines, crushed concrete powder) and combine them into composite formulations. The Digital Lab automates the creation of mortar or concrete recipes, enabling rapid iteration on sustainable mixes while incorporating key parameters such as CO₂ footprint, cost, and physical properties.

2. **AI Optimization (Sequential Learning Engine):**

SLAMD employs sequential learning algorithms (e.g., Gaussian Process Regression, Random Forest) to iteratively propose formulations predicted to meet user-defined targets. These targets may, e.g. include compressive strength (fc28d), maximum recycled content, and reduced environmental impact. The platform supports exploration vs. exploitation tuning, allowing users to shift between novel formulations (explore) and high-confidence predictions (exploit) depending on the optimization phase.

SLAMD has been validated in real laboratory environments, achieving Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 6. It has demonstrated superior efficiency compared to traditional design methods, significantly reducing the number of required experiments. The

³¹ C. Völker *et al.*, "Data driven design of alkali-activated concrete using sequential learning," *J. Clean. Prod.*, vol. 418, p. 138221, Sep. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.138221.

³² C. Völker *et al.*, ACCELERATING THE SEARCH FOR ALKALI ACTIVATED CEMENTS WITH SEQUENTIAL LEARNING. 2022. doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33502.92480/1.

platform is open-source (MIT License) and accessible as both a local Python tool and a web-hosted application, making it adaptable for diverse user needs and fostering broad adoption across research and industry^{33, 34}

SLAMD is not only a technical tool but represents a paradigm shift in sustainable materials design, enabling stakeholders to bridge theoretical innovation with real-world application and drive forward circular construction practices.

7.2.1. Tools to be tested

This demo is intended to show how SLAMD supports the development of a mortar based on two construction waste materials from RAS. The materials used are pulverized flat glass waste, which cannot be used to produce new flat glass due to its chemical composition. Figure 22 shows where in the flat glass recycling process the pulverized residue is generated. In addition, grinded concrete fines from the construction demolition waste is used, which would otherwise have to be sent to landfill.

Figure 22: The glass residue used in SLAMD is generated during quality assurance

³³ BAMresearch/WEBSLAMd. (Feb. 28, 2025). Python. Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und -prüfung. Accessed: Mar. 19, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/BAMresearch/WEBSLAMd>

³⁴ "SLAMD - Materials Discovery." Accessed: Mar. 19, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://slamd-demo.herokuapp.com/materials/discovery>

The aim is to use both materials as a substitute for cement to reduce the cement content – and thus the CO₂-intensive clinker content – in the mortar. The goal is to achieve a substitution rate of at least 30 mass percent while maintaining a compressive strength of at least 30 MPa. SLAMD will be used to identify as many different mortar formulations as possible that meet these requirements.

The material design space defined for this demonstration includes several tuneable parameters. The glass fines content varies between 5% and 40%, and the concrete fines content ranges from 5% to 30%, both in 2.5–5% increments. The total binder amount is varied between 300 and 360 kg/m³, the water-to-binder (w/b) ratio spans from 0.4 to 0.6, and the superplasticizer (SP) dosage ranges from 0% to 0.1% of the total mix. These parameters were selected based on practical feasibility and known physical limits and define the search space for SLAMD's iterative optimization of mortar formulations that maximize cement substitution while maintaining structural integrity.

Due to the absence of prior data in the Ragn-Sells demo case, SLAMD initially uses a Euclidean distance-based similarity method to suggest starting formulations. These are experimentally tested by Ragn-Sells, and results (e.g., fc28d values) are manually re-integrated into SLAMD to refine the predictive model. Through 6–8 iterative cycles, the software continuously improves its formulation proposals, supporting multi-objective optimization aligned with technical and economic feasibility.

In the Ragn-Sells demo, the following tools and functionalities within the SLAMD platform will be tested to evaluate their effectiveness in developing sustainable mortar formulations with high levels of cement substitution:

1. **Initial Formulation Suggestion (Pre-SLAMM Similarity-Based Selection):**

As SLAMD cannot operate without initial training data, the first set of formulations for this demo was generated externally using a Euclidean distance-based similarity approach. This pre-processing step identified feasible starting points by comparing the Ragn-Sells design space to previously known material systems. These formulations were tested in the lab to produce the initial experimental data required for SLAMD to begin its sequential learning process. This external step is not part of SLAMD itself and is not being evaluated as a tool, but rather served to enable SLAMD's application in a data-scarce scenario.

2. **Design Space Management and Adaptation**

This feature enables the flexible definition and adjustment of the formulation space, including parameters such as glass fines percentage, concrete fines percentage, superplasticizer content, water/binder ratio, and total binder amount. In the RAS demo, this functionality has been used to ensure that the proposed mixtures remain experimentally feasible and cover a broad but meaningful range of material combinations.

3. **Sequential Learning Engine:**

After receiving test results, this module enables iterative optimization by learning from previous data and updating formulation proposals. Its performance in reducing experimental cycles while achieving both technical ($f_{c28d} \geq 30$ MPa) and sustainability ($\geq 30\%$ cement substitution) goals will be monitored over 6–8 cycles.

4. **Explore vs. Exploit Mode Selection:**

SLAMD provides an option to adjust the explore-exploit balance, where “explore” mode emphasizes novelty and diversity in formulation proposals, and “exploit” mode prioritizes high-confidence, high-performance formulations. This feature will be tested for its utility in different phases of the optimization, especially when moving from initial exploration to targeted refinement.

5. **Manual Feedback Loop for Experimental Results:**

SLAMD’s workflow includes a manual process in which compressive strength test results provided by Ragn-Sells are inserted back into the system to update the design space and inform subsequent formulation proposals. While not a tool itself, this feedback mechanism has been essential to the iterative optimization process.

7.2.2. Summary of hypotheses to evaluate in demonstration 2

The Ragn-Sells / BAM demo uses SLAMD to iteratively optimize mortar formulations incorporating recycled glass and concrete fines. The objective is to achieve a cement replacement rate of at least 30% while maintaining a minimum 28-day compressive strength (f_{c28d}) of 30 MPa.

1. Feasibility Hypothesis:

SLAMD can identify feasible mortar formulations with $\geq 30\%$ cement substitution using recycled inputs (glass and concrete fines) that achieve $f_{c28d} \geq 30$ MPa.

Validation: Cycles will be run to explore select formulations; further cycles will be run in the exploitation mode and are intended to further identify mixes with (if possible) high replacement rates

2. Optimization Hypothesis:

Iterative SLAMD cycles (6–8 total) will improve formulation quality over time by increasing the number of valid mixes that meet the target ($f_{c28d} \geq 30$ MPa) and by narrowing the range of compressive strength outcomes — i.e., reducing performance variability between formulations.

Validation: Improvement will be evaluated by analyzing how compressive strength (f_{c28d}) evolves across SLAMD cycles, focusing on trends in average values, minimum values, and the spread (standard deviation) of results within each cycle.

3. Parameter Influence Observation (Optional):

It is expected that parameters such as glass/concrete fines ratio, superplasticizer content, water/binder ratio, and binder mass influence the compressive strength (f_{c28d}) of the tested formulations. While the parameters were not systematically varied in a controlled manner, exploratory observations may reveal correlations between these variables and performance outcomes.

4. Explore-Exploit Strategy Hypothesis:

Use of SLAMD's explore mode in early cycles and exploit mode in later cycles enhances the balance between discovering novel formulations and optimizing known high performers.

Validation approach: Effectiveness of this strategy will be assessed by analyzing the diversity of proposed formulations and the progression in success rates across SLAMD cycles.

7.3. Value flow 3: Flat glass to flat glass

This third demonstration focuses on illustrating a circular value flow where flat glass from existing buildings is recovered, processed, and used to produce new flat glass, ultimately

reinstalled as a window component. The aim is to show how both the physical movement of materials and the flow of information are essential for enabling circularity. A key aspect of circular physical flows is the timely exchange of accurate data. Each actor in the value chain must be able to share and access relevant information at the right moment. In this context, the demonstration highlights how material can be traced both physically and digitally across different steps in the value chain.

The demonstration also shows how Circular Value Flow Planning (CVFP), along with the required digital capabilities, is integrated into the CP-IM platform. This includes using data for circularity assessments and strategic material planning.

While *Value Flow 1: Inventory of the Built Environment* emphasizes the initial step of data collection from existing structures, the flat glass to flat glass demonstrator continues from that point, focusing on the downstream stages of the circular process, as illustrated in Figure 23 below.

Figure 23: The part of the physical flow that the demonstration will focus on

7.3.1. Tools to be tested

Data generated in processes and operations

To enable effective circular value flow planning (CVFP), selected data from Ragn-Sells' Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) and Customer Relationship Management (CRM)

systems will be uploaded to the CP-IM platform. These systems provide essential input for mapping and managing circular processes in the flat glass value chain. The inventory of the building is a vital data source, collected as described in *Value flow 1: Inventory of the material bank*, is sent to the CP-IM platform according to the different methods explained in chapter 7.1. Information about the building from which the windows are dismantled will be provided by the facility owner's database or Ragn-Sells EPR system. Product data from across the value chain will be collected from databases or files which will be uploaded to the CP-IM platform.

The ERP system consolidates core business data, including information on products, materials, services, and logistics. It serves as a central source for understanding operational aspects such as material volumes, weights, transportation routes, and incoming orders. In this project, data related to orders, material specifications, logistics, and transport will be extracted from ERP systems to support accurate planning and decision-making.

The CRM system contains customer-specific information, which is also relevant in a circular context. Since the definition of the "customer" may vary depending on the role of each actor in the circular value chain, the CRM system becomes an important tool for managing stakeholder interactions and responsibilities. In this project, customer-related data—such as ownership and order number—will be retrieved from CRM systems to support coordination across the chain.

PLM systems are designed to manage and share data throughout the entire lifecycle of a product—from design and manufacturing to use, maintenance, and end-of-life. These systems offer significant potential to support data integration in circular material paths by providing detailed product information across different stages.

However, in this project, PLM systems are not included. Although their use was initially anticipated during the application phase, it became evident that the actors involved in the flat glass and concrete flows do not currently utilize PLM systems in their operations. As a result, these systems were excluded from the data integration strategy for this demonstration.

Data generated from inventory

The data collected in the inventory is used as input in this value flow, see chapter 7.1 above.

Data generated from sensors

The scales of Ragn-Sells are connected to an internal system, Viktoria, that controls the weight of every vehicle delivering material and resources to a site. In the system the weight is connected to a specific fraction related to the customer profile and agreement. This weight of a specific fraction is shared with the ERP system.

External databases

To populate the flat glass information already available from other systems with CO₂ data, a database provided by the Swedish National Board of Housing, Building and Planning will be used and connected to the CP-IM platform. External database with instructions for dismantling is also planned to connect with the CP-IM platform.

Data from actors in the value chain

Actors across the value chain will be required to upload datasheets into the CP-IM platform. For example, this includes flat glass manufacturers that use recycled cullet in production, as well as window manufacturers incorporating that recycled flat glass into new products. To ensure consistency and interoperability, these datasheets must follow standardized templates that align with the CP-IM ontology. This structured approach enables efficient data sharing and supports traceability and circularity assessments throughout the value chain.

7.3.2. Data flow hypothesis

The data flow enables traceability in the entire value chain and makes it possible to estimate the volumes of flat glass that are available.

The described data flow for flat glass to flat glass recycling starts with the questions if there is a valid agreement with a facility owner (or its contractors), to enable an inventory and a collection of windows. The collected data from the inventory makes it possible to estimate volumes for each recycling scenario with CVFP. Dismantling of windows for flat glass recycling needs to be done in a careful way and there are specific instructions on how this should be done. This information needs to be provided to the dismantler before dismantling the windows, preferably through the CP-IM platform.

Further, the windows need to be transported to a site as whole windows on specific stands or carefully placed on an EU-stool, otherwise there is a risk for contamination. This information is also a part of the dismantling instructions and information that is required when purchasing this service.

An order to collect the windows is created when a notification is given through Ragn-Sells ERP that windows are ready for collection. This triggers a route planning event in the route planning system at Ragn-Sells.

Once the windows have arrived at a designated Ragn-Sells facility, their weight is measured which generates a data point in the ERP system.

In the pre-treatment the flat glass is crushed out of the frames to cullet. The weight of the cullet from the pretreatment is measured on a scale, the scale generates a data point to the ERP system. The cullet is then transferred to quality assurance where it is separated in different fractions:

- 1) End of Waste cullet, the quality assured product
- 2) Residue
- 3) Reject: small pieces of wood etc.

The End of Waste cullet is packed for and its weight measured on a scale which is connected to Ragn-Sells ERP system and then sent to the flat glass producer. The residue is also weighted.

The recycled cullet is mixed for production of new flat glass, and the amount of recycled content is notified. The flat glass produced will keep the information of amount of recycled content, to be able to share this with the other actors in the value chain. This information can be presented in an EPD (Environmental Product Declaration).

The flat glass is processed and tailored for the right purpose and more information about the flat glass is added. The flat glass is put into new windows and the information about the recycled content is communicated to the market.

Windows with information about recycled content are mounted in new buildings.

Figure 24 below shows an overview of the data flow, from where data is collected or where data is generated. The appendix 1 has an URL leading to a high resolution image that can be studied further.

Figure 24: Data flow hypothesis for flat glass to flat glass (for high resolution image see URL in appendix 3)

The values/outputs of the process are:

- Dismantling descriptions provided to user
- Amount of flat glass in the built environment available for flat glass recycling
- Amount of flat glass collected from a specific building/project

- Amount of flat glass from a specific project that was treated and quality assured as an EoW (End of Waste) product
- CO₂-savings due to recycling of flat glass
- Amount of virgin material replaced with recycled cullet
- Amount of flat glass produced with recycled cullet available on the market

In this demonstration the data flow and CVFP module shall be integrated with the CP-IM platform, Re Suite and Mainflux IoT platform, to deliver the values/outputs described.

7.3.3. Summary of hypothesis to evaluate in demonstration 3

- The CP-IM platform has the capability to enable traceability in the entire value chain given that the required data is uploaded.
- The CVFP module can estimate how much flat glass cullet that is available for flat glass production.
- The CVFP module can estimate how much flat glass that are available for window production.
- The CVFP module can verify the estimated volumes with real data.
- The CVFP module can estimate how much CO₂ that can be saved by choosing flat glass recycling.
- The CVFP module can verify the CO₂ savings using real data.
- The capabilities for delivering above values and CVFP are existing.

7.4. Value flow 4: Reuse of flat glass

The case for reusing windows is delicate and will not be part of any demonstration. However, together with TUB and 3L we have gone deeper into the possibilities of future reuse systems for windows.

7.4.1. Process map for reuse of flat glass

The process map for the reuse of flat glass including energy inputs and corresponding emissions associated with the manufacture of glass products include: raw material sourcing and processing (stage 1), raw material processing (stage 2), primary product forming stage (stage 3) and secondary flat glass processing (stage 4) -see graphic below.

The manufacture of glass products involves multiple energy-intensive stages, each contributing to significant greenhouse gas emissions. In Stage 1 (Raw Material Sourcing and Transport), energy is consumed during the extraction and transportation of key inputs such as silica sand, soda ash, and limestone. Emissions at this stage arise primarily from diesel-fueled mining equipment and transport logistics, accounting for an estimated 5–10% of the total carbon footprint. Stage 2 (Raw Material Processing) involves cleaning, grinding, and batching materials, typically powered by electricity and fossil fuels, contributing moderately to energy use but with relatively lower emissions compared to melting. Stage 3 (Primary Product Forming)—the float glass production process—is the most energy- and emissions-intensive stage, requiring sustained furnace temperatures above 1,500°C. Natural gas or electricity powers these furnaces, and this stage can account for over 70% of the total energy consumption and CO₂ emissions in flat glass manufacturing. Finally, Stage 4 (Secondary Processing) includes cutting, tempering, coating, laminating, or insulating glass units, depending on the application. While energy requirements here are lower than in Stage 3, secondary processing still contributes to the overall footprint due to heating elements and coating technologies. Combined, these four stages can result in total emissions of approximately 0.8 to 1.2 tons of CO₂ per ton of flat glass produced, highlighting the importance of energy efficiency and decarbonization strategies throughout the glass value chain.

Figure 25: Mapping the flat glass value chain Rebecca Hartwel et. al

Flat glass production relies on a precise combination of natural raw materials, additives, and recycled content. The resource inputs used not only determine the chemical and

physical properties of the final product but also influence the environmental footprint of the entire manufacturing process. Understanding these material inputs is essential for assessing sustainability, optimizing production, and enabling circular practices such as cullet (glass shard) recycling and reuse.

Primary Raw Materials

Flat glass is made through the float glass process, where raw materials are melted at high temperatures to form a continuous sheet. The key resource inputs include:

- Silica Sand (SiO_2):
Comprising around 70–75% of the batch, silica sand is the primary component and provides the structural framework of the glass.
- Soda Ash (Na_2CO_3):
Makes up approximately 12–15% of the mix. It acts as a flux, lowering the melting point of silica to reduce energy consumption during processing.
- Limestone (CaCO_3):
Typically around 8–10% of the batch. It stabilizes the silica network and improves chemical durability and hardness.
- Dolomite ($\text{CaMg}(\text{CO}_3)_2$):
Provides magnesium and calcium, further enhancing thermal and chemical resistance.
- Alumina (Al_2O_3):
Added in small amounts to improve chemical resistance and reduce devitrification.

Secondary Inputs and Additives

The key secondary inputs include:

- Cullet (Recycled Glass):
Increasingly used in modern production, cullet can constitute 15–60% of the input mix. It melts at a lower temperature than raw materials, saving energy and reducing CO_2 emissions. High cullet content also promotes a circular production model.
- Coloring Agents:
Metallic oxides such as iron (green/gray), cobalt (blue), or selenium (bronze) are added to alter the visual and solar control properties of the glass.

- Refining Agents:
Sulfates and chlorides (e.g., Na_2SO_4 , NaCl) are used to remove gas bubbles from the molten glass during melting.

Energy and Process Inputs

- While not materials per se, energy inputs are critical to processing materials:
- Natural Gas and Electricity: Used to heat furnaces to 1,500–1,600°C.
- Oxygen (in oxy-fuel furnaces): Improves combustion efficiency and reduces NO_x emissions.

Conclusion

Flat glass production depends on high-quality mineral resources and increasing volumes of recycled cullet. As environmental concerns grow, resource efficiency, alternative raw materials, and greater cullet use are key levers for reducing the carbon intensity of the industry while maintaining performance standards.

Figure 26: Mapping the flat glass value chain in the UK Rebecca Hartwel et. al

7.4.2. Material path for reuse of flat glass

A well-structured material path model (MPM) is critical for transitioning from linear to circular use of flat glass in construction. This model tracks the physical movement of flat glass from production through use, deconstruction, processing, and reintegration, enabling reuse at scale. The goal is to minimize waste, preserve material integrity, and streamline logistics to support a circular economy.

Stages of the Material Path Model

1. Production and Installation

Flat glass is manufactured via the float process, typically in standard sizes and performance grades (e.g., tempered, laminated, low-E coated).

During new construction, glass panels are selected, framed, and installed in façades, windows, or interior partitions. Panels should be installed with disassembly in mind, using reversible fastening systems and non-permanent sealants.

2. Use Phase and Monitoring

Glass remains in use for 20–50 years. During this time, regular maintenance and inspections help preserve reuse potential. Building operators should keep records (ideally digital) of the components' condition and specifications for future recovery.

3. Selective Deconstruction

At end-of-use, buildings undergo controlled deconstruction, rather than demolition. Trained teams remove glass panels intact, using specialized lifting tools and minimizing damage. Panels are sorted based on size, coating, and condition, separating reuse-grade from recycling-grade materials.

4. Inspection and Cleaning

Removed panels are inspected for cracks, scratches, and coating degradation. Reuse-grade glass is cleaned and refurbished (e.g., removing old seals or frames). Panels are graded into categories such as “as-is reuse,” “recutting required,” or “unsuitable.”

5. Storage and Logistics

Salvaged glass is stored in protective racks at reuse centres or warehouses. Efficient logistics are essential to reduce handling damage and emissions—regional reuse hubs can optimize transportation.

6. Redistribution and Reuse

Refurbished glass enters the market via reuse platforms, either sold directly or matched to new building projects. Panels may be recut or reframed to fit new architectural designs, provided safety standards are met.

7. Recycling (Fallback Path)

If panels are unsuitable for reuse, they are directed to closed-loop recycling (e.g., remelting into new float glass) or downcycled into lower-grade products like insulation.

Key Enablers for the MPM are:

- Design for Disassembly in new buildings
- Regional reuse infrastructure (collection, processing, storage)
- Standardized quality grading systems
- Policy incentives and procurement standards
- Collaborative platforms as the REINCARNATE CP-IM enabling demolition contractors, architects, and reuse suppliers to co-create, to monitor and to steer the MPM.

This MPM aligns with circular construction goals, extending the life of valuable glass products while reducing the environmental burden of raw material extraction and glass production.

7.4.3. Data flow for reuse of flat glass

To scale the reuse of flat glass in the construction industry, a robust and transparent data flow model is essential. This model enables stakeholders to track, assess, and exchange glass components across their lifecycle, from installation to deconstruction and reintegration into new buildings. The proposed data flow model centres on digital integration, traceability, and interoperability.

Key Components of the Data Flow Model (DFM) are:

1. Material Tagging and Identification

Input: At manufacturing or installation, flat glass panels are assigned a unique digital ID (QR code, RFID tag, or digital twin). Data Captured: Manufacturer, dimensions, coatings, thermal performance, safety ratings, installation date, and location.

2. Building Information Modeling (BIM) Integration

Digital IDs are integrated into BIM models of the building.

Enables real-time tracking of flat glass throughout the building's lifespan and allows easy extraction of specifications during renovation or demolition planning.

3. Condition Assessment and Grading

Upon building renovation or demolition, glass panels are scanned and inspected (physically and digitally) using tools like image recognition, sensors, or manual input.

Data updated in a centralized database: integrity rating, presence of coatings or sealants, and reuse suitability.

4. Digital Material Passports

Each panel is assigned a material passport containing performance data, usage history, test results, and reuse certifications.

Shared across stakeholders via cloud-based platforms, enhancing trust and regulatory compliance.

5. Marketplace and Matching Systems

Salvaged flat glass is listed on digital reuse marketplaces.

Data such as size, quality, quantity, and location is used by algorithmic matching systems to pair available panels with design needs in new construction projects.

6. Feedback Loop and Analytics

Data on reuse frequency, failure rates, carbon savings, and economic performance is fed back into industry-wide dashboards for monitoring and optimization.

Enables stakeholders to adjust practices, designs, and policies to improve reuse outcomes.

Summary

To effectively scale the reuse of flat glass within the construction sector, a digitally integrated and transparent data flow model is essential. This model enables stakeholders to track and evaluate glass components throughout their lifecycle—from production and installation to deconstruction and reintegration. Central to the model are unique digital identifiers (e.g., QR codes or RFID tags), which link each panel to detailed data captured and maintained within Building Information Modeling (BIM) systems. Upon renovation or demolition, condition assessments inform digital material passports that document reuse suitability and history. These passports feed into digital marketplaces where algorithmic matching systems connect salvaged panels with new construction needs. Finally, analytics provide feedback on performance, carbon savings,

and economic outcomes, allowing continuous improvement and informed decision-making across the value chain.

8. Conclusion

The global extraction and use of raw materials have surged threefold since 1970, with only a small fraction being reintegrated into the economy through circular processes. The construction industry stands out as a major consumer of these materials and a key contributor to environmental degradation. Despite high sorting rates, effective recycling remains limited due to regulatory gaps, lack of standardized practices, inconsistent data, and missing documentation for reuse.

To counter this, the concept of circular value flow planning is proposed, emphasizing systems thinking to extend material lifecycles, maximize resource value, and embed critical data at each stage, from inventory to reintroduction into another building. The approach is showcased through the CP-IM platform, which integrates tools and ontologies to support real-time, high-quality decisions about reuse, recycling, and associated environmental impacts.

Concrete examples are provided through the flat glass industry, whose high carbon footprint and complex recycling constraints underscore the urgency of innovation. Demonstrations focus on closed-loop recycling systems and AI-assisted optimization of recycled material mixtures. Flat glass recycling processes, especially when data-rich and quality-controlled, can yield significant CO₂ savings and substitute virgin materials effectively. Demonstrating emerging tools like BIM for circular value flow planning and SLAMD aim to show how digitalization can accelerate material recovery, recycling and reuse, while also validating hypotheses about inventory methods, performance prediction, and explore cycles in material formulation.

Ultimately, the path toward circularity hinges on transparent information flow, shared standards, and collaborative platforms like CP-IM that turn the built environment into a repository of valuable, reusable resources, allowing materials like flat glass to retain their systemic value and contribute meaningfully to climate neutrality goals.

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APPENDIX

Appendix I – The different data flows in demo 1: Upstream inventory of material bank

Please see high resolution version of:

- Figure 27: Data flow hypothesis for method 1a
- Figure 28: Data flow hypothesis for method 1b
- Figure 29: Data flow hypothesis for method 2
- Figure 30: Data flow hypothesis for method 3

In the following URL: [Reincarnate _ Public Appendix • Business Dev Rec](#)

Appendix II - Data flow hypothesis for demo 3: flat glass to flat glass

Please see high resolution version of:

- Figure 31: Data flow hypothesis for flat glass to flat glass

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Appendix IV – The different data flows in demo 1: Upstream inventory of material bank

Please see high resolution version of:

- Figure 32. The defined steps to identify circular value flow planning and the questions to answer in each step.

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Appendix V – Alternative glass recovery scenarios

Appendix VI – The overview of modules in CP-IM

